

DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHY

**Assessment of the Onshore Environmental Impact of
Offshore Wind Farms: A Case Study of Triton Knoll,
Lincolnshire**

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ABSTRACT

In current times, wind farms are dramatically expanding in the UK. In many regions, people express strong opposition to the operation and installation of wind turbines. This dissertation investigates and evaluates the onshore environmental impact of offshore wind farms with the intention of providing a deeper insight into the reasons underpinning the concerns of local residents regarding this development.

The focus of this research is limited to the Triton Knoll wind farm site in Lincolnshire. Questionnaire responses strongly suggest that renewable energy, including the exploitation of wind power is well regarded amongst local residents. Nevertheless, the proposed substation site is currently the subject of intense scrutiny and forceful opposition, particularly in relation to its potential environmental impact.

Data on noise, land protection status and other related factors indicates that the location is a suitable area and that noise should not be of concern to the residents. However, analysis of maps and interview data indicates that it is likely that there will be a considerable effect upon landscape substances and visual receivers. Moreover, the development will potentially have a considerable impact upon nature and ecological conservation.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

The primary focus of this dissertation is to investigate local community opinions regarding the onshore environmental impacts, resultant from offshore wind developments, with the intention of understanding the reasons underpinning the concerns. It stresses, in particular, upon quantifying certain key aspects of environmental problems that can result from wind farm-related plans and projects. These environmental concerns include their visual impact upon the landscape, which could damage a natural site; sound pollution and the impact they may have upon biodiversity, even though they may be in an optimum position. The final analysis of wind farm development revolves around assessing both the pros and cons in an unbiased and logical manner.

Over the last 25 years, exploitation of the natural environment has changed dramatically following the discovery of new resources suitable for power generation. A clean and arguably more effective method of producing electricity has become prominent after the Non-Fossil Fuel Obligation (NFFO), which was implemented as part of the 1989 Electricity Action in the United Kingdom.

Electrical power consumption is becoming increasingly important in society, especially in advanced countries. This is due to each aspect of our everyday life increasingly becoming more dependent upon electricity.

Overexploitation of non-renewable resources of energy such as the burning of fossil fuel is predicted to lead to a lack of these resources in the future. Renewable forms of energy are increasingly seen as an alternative source. A multitude of wind spots worldwide have been utilised to harvest wind power and to convert it into electricity.

This dissertation aims to investigate and evaluate the perceptions of residents living close to a potential wind farm substation. Gathering data was achieved by a range of different methods including carrying out a questionnaire investigating the onshore environmental impacts of the offshore wind farm in Triton Knoll and to find out more about the concerns shown by local residents towards the proposed setting of a substation in their local area. Secondly, the potential amount of visual disturbance resulting from wind turbines on neighbouring households was determined via examining the construction company's documents and maps, and interviewing local residents, action groups and the construction company's

representatives about their opinions related to this issue. A field visit was also made to the study area to obtain a further insight on the ground and to estimate the biodiversity of the natural environment there. Finally, by reviewing secondary sound and wind data, the amount of annoyance caused by the noise released from wind turbines and an estimation of the level of land protection in the site will be gauged.

Arguments based on the above aims are developed in order to provide a justification regarding whether it is viable to keep investing in wind energy. The motivation for this dissertation came from two sources. Firstly, an article on the National Trust website called Triton Knoll Offshore Wind Farm (Appendix A), which gave an insight into the scale and environmental significance of the Triton Knoll project; and secondly, a documentary movie, Fears over Pylon Plan for Lincolnshire Coast (Lincolnshire Citizens, 2010) where the East Lindsey District Council said that tourism would be harmfully affected by the 80.5 km route cables to transfer electricity from offshore wind farms. Throughout the movie, concerns were raised that the East Coast of Lincolnshire, close to a region of natural beauty, could turn into an area full of power pylons. Having a previous interest and an academic background in renewable power and the potential impact on the environment, it was very appealing to investigate the local community opinions about offshore wind developments with the intention of understanding the reasons for their concerns.

Wind power has been used for at least 7000 years (Sahin, 2004). Since 1979, wind turbines have been constructed to generate electricity. Wind farms, as a renewable source of energy, have played a vital role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, which are the most important cause of anthropogenic-driven global climate change and in decreasing the cost of producing energy. However, the construction and function of wind farms do have harmful impacts on the environment (Coles and Taylor, 1993). In recent years the debate, attention and discussion around wind farms have dramatically increased.

This research project will now concentrate on areas of study under the titles: community attitude, visibility analysis, noise, and land protection position. Each section will describe the relevant methodology and subsequent results.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

Defining Wind Farms

Over the last twenty years, advancements in renewable power technologies have succeeded in transforming the power of wind, wave, sunlight and tide into a useful source of energy that can be stored and used for everyday life in the UK. Although renewable power provides 'cleaner' alternatives for electricity than burning fossil fuel, each source has an impact on the environment. Generating electricity using wind power is a comparatively new practice despite wind energy having been used for thousands of years for both windmills and sailing ships. However, wind farms are experiencing a dramatic growth but their environmental impacts are proving to be a controversial issue.

Wind farms can be defined as a group of several turbines that generate electricity. These wind structures, can be placed once certain requirements are met in an area of open countryside. They are tall constructions up to 80m in height that can modify the nature of the landscape and predominate over its beauty (Coles and Taylor, 1993).

Hedger (1995) defines wind farms as human-made structures that engage a multitude of turbines that emit noise; they are tall, their parts can be moved, their base needs to extend far below the Earth's surface and they require wide streets to be transferred and detailed planning when deciding on locations. Ibenholt (2002) mentions that wind farms in the UK consist of between 3 and 40 turbines.

In 1992, the first wind farm to be utilised in a commercial manner was introduced in the UK. Substantial development of this technology has occurred since then. Nowadays, wind turbines perform with one-fifth of the downtime and supply about one-third more power per unit of energy, yet cost approximately half the price (Martinez and Prats, 1999).

Apparently, the development of wind turbines seems to be infinite. This can be seen from the further progression in the development and design procedures by engineers to increase the efficiency of producing electricity and to decrease sound emissions.

The Increasingly Importance of Wind Farms

Nowadays, it is essential that electrical energy is accessible for users upon request. Bellarmine and Urquhart (1996) state that without electricity, our life will be in inevitable suspension. Therefore, why does wind energy seem to be of great interest as one of the most appropriate means of producing energy in the UK in the present day? As mentioned by Hedger (1995) that the UK owns the finest wind resource in Europe. It consequently appears that policymakers have taken advantage of such a rich natural resource.

Wind Energy in Europe

The construction and operation of wind power installations in Europe has experienced dramatic and sustained development during the last 20 years. In 2009, wind energy contributed to 4.8% of the EU's total electricity consumption (Figure 1). Fast growth in using wind energy has been attributed to the need for Europe to have a sufficient source of energy that is not dependent on gas or oil, which in-turn contributes to reducing greenhouse gas emissions (The European Wind Energy Association (EWEA), 2008).

Figure 1: EU Installed power capacity from 2000 to 2007 (MW) – (EWEA, 2008)

Wind farms are playing a significant role in alleviating climate change as it is a clean and renewable source of energy, which is simultaneously beneficial in terms of decreasing the water consumption used in cooling processes and decreasing air pollutant emissions connected to several conventional power production technologies (Ibenholt, 2002).

The Political schema for Promoting Renewable Power Sources of the EU

Renewable energy and climate change are equally important in the context of the EU Policy Framework. The EU's renewable energy position dates from 1997 when it adopted the

Commission's White Paper entitled 'Energy for the future: renewable sources of energy' (Commission of the European Communities (COM), 1997). After that, the Commission recommended some climate change and renewable energy goals under several key targets, which seem to be aspiring and far-reaching. These targets obtained political consent of the EU leaders in December 2008 (European Union Committee (EUC), 2008).

The EU Members were committed to achieving the following targets:

- Increasing the share of renewable energy to 20% of Europe's total energy sources use by 2020, including 10% renewable energy in transportation;
- Reducing greenhouse gas emissions by at least 20% by 2020 compared to 1990 levels (if other industrial countries make similar attempts in the scheme of a new global climate change consensus, cutting the emissions should rise to 30%); and,
- Increasing energy efficiency through decreasing consumption by 20% by 2020.

It is clear that over a relatively short period, the new EU goals demand a considerable change in renewable energy progression. As can be seen from table 1, by 2020, it is expected that 20% of all electricity consumption will come from renewable sources, of which approximately 12% will be from wind energy (EUC, 2008).

This would require an increase in the present portion that wind power has in the EU's electricity use by 3x the amount. One of the explanations as to why wind energy has expanded dramatically in the last 20 years is that the wind power industry has developed so rapidly. This development occurred in the turbine capacity; onshore turbines have grown from 50 KW in the 1980s to more than 3 MW in the present day. The average rotor diameter has increased from around 15m to an average of 100m or more (COM, 2006). Around 90% of the EU wind turbine marketplace is generated by turbines that create between 750 - 3000 KW and consist of 3 blades upwind. Wind turbines' installation costs have also declined considerably over time which has not just made wind farms more attainable but also attractive to more investors (Sahin, 2004).

Table 1: National overall share and targets of renewable resources of 2005, 2009 and 2020 (European Commission Energy, 2009)

	Renewable energy %		
	2005	2009 (prov.)	2020 target
Austria	23,3	29.2	34
Belgium	2,2	3.8	13
Bulgaria	9,4	11.5	16
Cyprus	2,9	3.8	13
Czech Rep	6,1	8.5	13
Denmark	17	19.7	30
Estonia	18	77.7	25
Finland	28,5	29.8	38
France	10,3	12.4	23
Germany	5,8	9.7	18
Greece	6,9	7.9	18
Hungary	4,3	9.5	13
Ireland	3,1	5.1	16
Italy	5,2	7.8	17
Latvia	32,6	36.8	40
Lithuania	15	16.9	23
Luxembourg	0,9	2.8	11
Malta	0	0.7	10
Netherlands	2,4	4.2	14
Poland	7,2	9.4	15
Portugal	20,5	25.7	31
Romania	17,8	21.6	24
Slovak Rep	6,7	10	14
Slovenia	16	17.5	25
Spain	8,7	13	20
Sweden	39,8	50.2	49
UK	1,3	2.9	15
EU27	8,5	11.6	20

Figure 2: The EU renewable power growth: electrical energy production from different sources by 2020(COM, 2006).

Overall, as can be seen from Figure 2, the EU wind farms' capacity has grown from 4,753 MW in 1997 to 74,767 MW in 2009. There will be an expansion of wind power in the short term, and, according to some predictions, full usage could go beyond 161GW by 2020. EWEA suggests even greater projections of approximately 230 GW by 2020 (COM, 2010).

Offshore Wind Power

Offshore wind farms are still in their early stages compared to onshore wind farms and only amount for around 2% of the entire existing wind power in Europe. The North Sea and the Baltic Sea are considered as suitable locations for most offshore wind farms and most of them go 30m below sea and are not further than 40 km off the coast. Offshore technology is more expensive since it is more complex to install turbines in an offshore location compared to onshore wind farms as it encounters very harsh environments (Gaudiosi, 1999). Furthermore, installation equipment is limited, which acts as a barrier in achieving such projects; moreover, there is a lack of ships or ports that can facilitate the installation; no adequate expert labour force, and difficulties in finding access to energy for the installation. However, offshore wind energy is expected to increase significantly in conjunction with technological advances, as the potential standard turbine size is increasing dramatically (Still, 2001). Indeed, it was suggested that by 2020, offshore wind power is expected to increase 30-40 times from its 2007 level of 1.1 GW (COM, 2007).

Environmental advantages of Wind Farms

Most of the evidence suggests that human activities are altering the climate (Bice, 2008). The Swedish chemist, Arrhenius (1896) was the first to mention the future impact of human

practices on the carbon cycle. He states that burning fossil fuels (coal, gas and oil) increases atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, which is an important greenhouse gas. According to him, increasing the temperature of the planet by 4-5°C can result from doubling the current amount of atmospheric CO₂ concentration (Arrhenius, 1896). After 60 years, Roger Revelle (an American oceanographer) recognised that it would be important to begin calculating atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. According to Revelle, human is effectively altering the climate by producing more Greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. (Revelle, 1956 in Keeling and Bacastow, 1977, page 78). Therefore, in the 1950s, Revelle and his colleague Charles Keeling initiated a monitoring of atmospheric CO₂ in Mauna Loa in Hawaii. Their experiment attracted the world's attention because of its impact on the global carbon cycle. A growth of 17 ppm of CO₂ concentration has been recorded since the start of this experiment in 1957 (Keeling and Bacastow, 1977). The consequent increase in atmospheric CO₂ has caused imbalance in the carbon cycle, as fossil fuel burning and cement production with land use changes transfer carbon to the atmosphere (Schimel and Wigley, 2000). Humans have been burning huge amounts of fossil fuels as a source of energy since the beginning of the Industrial Revolution. This amount is currently about 5 to 6 Gt C/yr (Bice, 2008), including CO₂ from cement production. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (1995) reports that from 1990 to 2100 there will be an increase of between 1.4 to 5.8 C⁰ in the Earth's temperature. This may cause sea levels to rise (IPCC, 1995 in Houghton, 1995).

The Contribution of Wind

Wind farms do not emit any CO₂ emissions or other gases throughout their function and minimal amounts during installation and manufacturing stages. EWEA indicates that in 2010, wind power contributed to 75,000 MW of the total electricity in 15 EU countries. This level increased from 40,000 MW in 2005 (European Wind Energy Association, 2006).

Estimating the reduction in CO₂ emissions that result from generating electricity from wind can be achieved through different processes. These processes rely on estimations made about the fuels, which will be replaced by wind power introduction into the power combination, a combination that is obviously different throughout the EU (EWEA, 2003). Notably, wind power cannot completely replace power stations. This is because power stations that burn fossil fuel are stable as they regularly produce electricity. Wind power is an instable type of energy; it shows erratic trends in production according to wind speeds (Holm-Jørgensen, Stærdahl and Nielsen, 2008). Nuclear power plants can be a very clear example of that because of their stability as their power cannot be simply increased or decreased, namely it is

always the same (Kessler, 2002). Therefore, there has to be a combination of fossil fuel power stations and wind power so that electricity stations can sustain a minimum supply at all times. The European Union estimates that every kilowatt per hour (kWh) generated by wind farms is equal to a kWh produced by a mix of gas, oil and coal. The International Energy Agency's (IEA) latest project estimates that in 2010, coal, oil and gas in the EU generated 1,827 Terawatt hours (TWh) of electricity. Of this quantity, 53 % was generated by coal-fired energy stations, 39 % from gas and 8 % from oil (EWEA, 2006). During this progression, 1,466 million tonnes of CO₂ is emitted from these sources of energy. This indicates that 0.802 million tonnes (Mt) of CO₂ emission can be preserved by generating 1 TWh from wind farms. However, it is expected that the burning of fossil fuels will be more efficient by 2020, in particular coal and the combination of utilising different sources of energy in Europe is estimated to adjust. For these reasons, it is expected that the reduction in CO₂ will decrease to 0.725 Mt, and by 2030 to 0.644 Mt. By 2030, oil will contribute to 2 % of the total mix, and coal (which generates almost double the amount of CO₂) as gas; will supply 41 %, followed by gas at 56 % (EWEA, 2006). By the end of 2005, 67 million tonnes of CO₂ emissions were reduced through the 40,500 MW contributions from wind farms in the EU. This amount of CO₂ contributes to 20 % of the EU's commitment toward the Kyoto Protocol. The new wind power capacity installed in the EU last year alone will diminish annual emissions by 11 million tonnes. Further on, throughout their total lifetime, the 6,183 MW of wind farms operated in 2005 alone will evade emissions of 200 million tonnes of CO₂. This is an equivalent of above 55% of the EU's commitment toward the Kyoto Protocol (COM, 2010). EWEA (2003) suggests that more than 30 % of the EU's Kyoto obligation is met by the operation of wind farms in the EU, resulting in a decrease in CO₂ emissions by 350 Mt in 2010. This is extremely significant towards tackling global warming.

Why are there protests against wind farms in the UK?

Survey evidence indicates that some people across the United Kingdom strongly oppose the operation and installation of wind turbines (Birnie et al., 1999; Khan, 2003). According to these opponents, wind farm development frequently causes many disadvantages varying from landscape damage as described by Pasqualetti, Gipe and Righter (2002a), noise disturbance as some people believe, and local biodiversity and wildlife harm, especially in rural areas as explored by Barrios and Rodriguez (2004) and Bishop (2003).

Activists argue that before constructing such a project, a discussion should be held between all the stakeholders in order to reach an agreement. Developers recently started to consider

this dialogue as a descriptive environmental impact assessment, which addresses most of the debated environmental concerns. The local planning authority is one of these stakeholders, which has to confirm the project (Burall, 2004).

Visual Impact on Landscape and Land Use

Notably, opponents argue that wind turbines are high objects that need to be placed in a standard location where they can benefit from predominant winds. This indicates that the possibility of them being visible from a moderately wide area is too high (Aslet, 2004).

The adverse impact of this is extremely subjective; being clearly visible is not equal to being invasive. Some people who love the UK's countryside express concerns about wind farms spoiling locations famous for their beauty (Pasqualetti, Gipe and Righter, 2002b; Burall, 2004). At the same time, others perceive them as urbane and beautiful, responsible for fewer environmental impacts and better for climate change (NFO System Three, 2002).

Indeed, landscape is mostly influenced by humans and has developed throughout history. Undoubtedly, human interference to nature has changed the visual view of the countryside. For example, roads or electricity networks are now being seen as part of the scenery. When retired, wind turbines can easily be disposed of and the previous environment of the landscape can be recovered (Pasqualetti, Gipe and Righter, 2002b). Certain locations, for instance, natural reserves or national parks can be excluded from installation sites. This is happening in many EU countries (Pasqualetti, Gipe and Righter, 2002b). However, some developers perceive optimum location of wind farms is less important as the energy they produce has priority over damage to the landscape. According to them, the operation stage of the turbines in a wind farm engage only approximately 1 % of the whole area compared to the construction stage. In addition, activities such as agriculture or tourism can continue almost adjacent to the bottom layer of the turbines (Yan et al., 2010). EWEA (2003) estimates that by 2030, 150 GW wind turbines that will operate in the EU will only occupy a few hundred square kilometres. According to them, manufacturers of wind turbines should still work on the turbines' aesthetic appearance, as public support will increase. In addition, certain computer software can imitate future wind turbines, which can assist manufacturers and designers to evaluate the potential visual impact. It should be noted that involving local communities with such projects has contributed to minimising pessimistic opinions among the public (McLaren, 2007).

Sound

Noise is an additional concern expressed by protestors, which must be taken into account when investigating wind farms. Pedersen (2010) illustrated that people who live near wind farms are exposed to a certain amount of annoyance caused by the sound of turbines. Khan (2003) stated that the noise emission can be classified into aerodynamic and mechanical sound. Development of wind turbines, especially their insulation, has made them more efficient in terms of their speed. The turning of blades contributes to almost all of the noise emitted by the turbine. The development in the generator and gearbox industries has resulted in lesser noisy parts. Further development in the design of the blade could further decrease the sound of a turbine (Arakawa et al., 2005).

Table 2 shows a comparison of the relative sound produced by wind turbines while working on an average distance of 350m and other sound sources, which may be heard regularly. Upon careful scrutiny of these findings, it can be noted that the sound produced from active wind turbines is lower than street traffic, trains, building activities and several other sources of manufacturing noise and slightly louder than rural night time background noise (BWEA, 2004).

Table 2: Illustrating the recorded degrees of different noise sources (BWEA, 2004).

Source/Activity	Indicative noise level aB (A)
Threshold of hearing	0
Rural night-time background	20-40
Quiet bedroom	35
Wind farm at 350m	35-45
Car at 40mph at 100m	55
Busy general office	60
Truck at 30mph at 100m	65
Pneumatic drill at 7m	95
Jet aircraft at 250m	105
Threshold of pain	140

It should be noted that The British Wind Energy Association (BWEA, 2004) is an association with a large number of members, who hold the attitude that a conversation can carry on normally under a wind turbine without the need to raise one's voice.

Swift-Hook (1989) also states that two agents contribute to noise volume; firstly, the area between the turbines and the houses and secondly the amount of sound released from the turbine. The permitted distance authorised by the government for any industrial noise emission is 300m away from houses and it is the same for wind turbines.

A field study about wind farms in Scotland indicated that pre-construction, 12 % of inhabitants living close to the locations considered that the turbines would create noise during installation, and just 1 % considered them noisy once they had began working. Certainly, local authorities should estimate the sound levels at any houses near the wind turbines to ensure that the turbines are located sufficiently far away to evade an undesirable amount of noise (Waye and Öhrström, 2002). Pederson and Waye (2007) studied the relations between noise and annoyance in different living environments. They state that living in a countryside environment compared to an urban area, raises the danger of perceiving and being disturbed by noise from adjacent wind farms. Even though wind turbines emit noise, it can be suggested that the specific level is remarkably low, in terms of environmental impact.

Wind Farms and Wildlife

Ecocentrism advocates are worried that severe impacts to animals in their natural environment can result from the operation of wind turbines. At the design stage for turbines, the potential threat that the wind farm can have on wildlife on the site is often estimated. Before positioning the turbines, a complete study of numerous alleviation methods is required to guarantee that the danger of avian effects is significantly diminished. Such studies are illustrated by Colson (1995) which contain prevention and impediment to the passageway, fly zones and spaces of concentrations for certain types of migrant birds. Fewer large turbines are developed so that the overall amount of unsafe movable parts have extensively decreased, providing the desired power capacity. Lastly, electric power transmission wires are situated underground, wherever achievable to significantly decrease the number of bird fatalities resulting from electric shock.

Dirksen, van der Winden and Spaans (1998) state that although birds can detect turbines, long rows of turbines have a potential barrier effect. In addition, wind farms are linked to power lines, a more important reason for bird fatality (Janss, 1999). Erickson, et al., (2001) estimates that every year 750,000–1,000,000 birds are found dead due to collision with electricity lines connected with wind farms in the Netherlands and from 130 to 174 million birds in the United States. Additionally, 400 raptors were killed annually along 100 km of electricity lines surrounding the Donana National Park in Spain (Ferrer, Riva and Castroviejo, 1991).

Concessions should be made to guarantee that migration and flying zones are barely disturbed. Determining the best sites for wind turbine installation is a hard task and mountainous areas, boggy lands and National Parks are chosen Sites of Specific Scientific Interest (SSSI's).

Figure 3: is a comparison of the UK' optimum wind resource map and the areas planned for landscape significance (Coles and Taylor, 1993, p207).

Although there is a high level of congruence, it can be seen from Figure 3 that land potential for installing wind turbines is limited. Despite the fact that various inconveniences are connected to wind turbines, it should be noted that 'wind energy is generally regarded as environmentally friendly, in particular when the damaging impact from conformist electrical power plants emissions that conclude burning of fossil fuel are considered' (Manwell, McGowan and Rogers, 2002). All over the UK, the number of wind farms being designed or instilled has grown dramatically. For these reasons, their environmental impacts have attracted a great deal of attention and therefore, residents are expected to have the right to say whether turbines should be installed in their 'back yard' or not.

Future of wind farms

Even though wind farms are growing rapidly in the UK, it appears that offshore wind farms are going to predominate in the following years. Most commonly, wind energy that takes place offshore is much more costly to set up and repair compared to onshore wind farms.

However, because offshore wind turbines are usually constructed several miles away from the coast, the power efficiency is greater than onshore wind farms because the wind speed is superior by the seaside. The decrease of environmental effects concerning visual impact and space restriction is another advantage for offshore wind farms (Pantaleo, et al., 2004). In comparison with onshore wind turbines, offshore wind turbines are often bigger, have taller diameter blades and their numbers are less. Gaudiosi (1999) illustrates that such development in the offshore turbines occur to profit from the faster wind speed that exists at higher latitudes, in addition, to reducing visual impact and to decrease the construction and energy transmission expenses. Still (2001) states that water depths for wind farms that take place out at sea should be between five and ten metres and it is preferable to be situated 5 km away from the coast. He uses the example of Blyth's offshore wind farm in Northumberland, which is the UK's earliest, as it faced severe weather off the North Sea. At primary examination, offshore wind farms have immense potential and attract far less disagreement from the public in general. However, as can usually be expected, some residents still do not support the idea.

Alternative Energy Production Resources

While switching from non-renewable to renewable power can be done by increasing the number of wind farms in the UK, in order to achieve the government's goals, other renewable technology methods can be used. As previously mentioned, the aim of this dissertation is to investigate and evaluate peoples' opinion about the environmental impact of offshore wind farms.

One enquiry should therefore be raised - are wind farms suitable to every location, or would other forms of renewable power be more beneficial to local residents?

Muneer, Asif and Kubie, (2003), for example, state that sunlight energy is nowadays acknowledged to be a very significant form of sustainable power in Great Britain that can be used effectively. Solar Photovoltaic (PV) energy is recognised as being a successful method for supplying clean and renewable energy. Solar power is definitely the biggest source of power on earth. Nevertheless, producing power using solar power plants is not efficient because the distributed waves emitted are not adequately powerful. In the 1970s, solar energy began to be used when oil sources started to deplete. This method of sustainable power

appears to be infinite, is non-detrimental to living creatures on earth and is 'clean' (Sen, 2004). One of the major concerns related to the installation of new and sustainable energy methods is the visual impact that they can cause. In an area where wind turbines supply energy to many households, it is possible for each household to own their own solar power panels, located above their houses in a method guaranteed not to cause any visual impact whereby each house can produce its own energy.

Solar energy can be used either by protecting buildings by surrounding it with a substance that decreases or prevents the loss of heat coming from the sun; heating water using solar panel collectors (rooftop), which accumulate the heat waves from the sun in a fluid storage technique; or, producing electricity by transferring solar energy into direct current electrical energy by semi-conductors that contain photovoltaic designed panels.. On the contrary to other methods of energy production, solar power plants appear to be safer to wildlife and may decrease landscape and nature invasion (Turney and Fthenakis, 2011).

Another form of renewable energy is hydropower, where the force of moving water is used to produce electricity. There is homogeneity between hydropower and wind power in terms of producing electricity as either transfer energy produced by motion from a mobile liquid or gas, principally into mechanical power and electrical energy in the following step Tidal energy is a method of hydropower that transfers the power of tides into electricity. The moon causes tidal flows and they have a massive potential for power production (Lang, 2003). This method of sustainable power is expected to supply an enormous share of the renewable energy production of the UK in the future. Where offshore wind farms are connected to impacts upon the environment, the same can be said about tidal energy methods. Although not as large physically, they can be seen out at sea and the possible effect that the rotating blades and loud machinery may have upon marine ecosystems is far greater than that of wind-powered turbines (Marsh, 2004). If tidal power site proposals were implemented in the near future, it would be very surprising if opposition were not shown towards the schemes (Lang, 2003).

Lastly, categorised as a non-renewable source of energy, nuclear power is still abundant and will be kept in reserve for future use. In 1956, Calder Hall in Cumbria was the initial power plant launched in the United Kingdom and in 2004, 14 nuclear power plants were in operation, supplying around 25% of energy supplies in Great Britain. However, since 1995, no recent locations have been developed (Pidgeon, Lorenzoni and Poortinga, 2008).

It is probably due to several problems linked to nuclear plants such as regulating the dangerous emissions of radiation resulting from atomic breakdown. According to Kessler (2002) the division of heavy atomic nucleus reactors discharge small amounts of radiation from the time of normal functioning, some of which is considered to be extremely radioactive. Table 3 demonstrates various quantities and levels of waste emitted by various types of power. Incidentally, it tends to draw attention to how wind energy is a 'clean' source of power.

Table 3: Presenting waste that is a result of various power generation methods (Kessler, 2002, p317)

	Non radio-active waste t/GWe'h	Low radio-active waste active m3/ GWe'h	High radioactive m3/ GWe'h
Coal	200	10-30	-----
Oil	7	Oil piping	-----
Gas	5	Gas piping	-----
Fission	6	$7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Fusion		$3.5 \cdot 10^{-1}$	-----
Hedro	20	-----	-----
Photo-voltaics	30	-----	-----
Wind	5	-----	-----

Nuclear fission holds infinite potential if managed properly, but the related to this method of power outweigh the benefits. In addition, nuclear fission can cause mortality or terminal sickness such as cancer and can gravely damage tourism, as happened in the 1986 Chernobyl disaster (Pidgeon, Lorenzoni and Poortinga, 2008). Although in the short-term, nuclear power plants can generate energy in a very efficient manner, scientists debate that the generation of electricity must confidently rely on sustainable forms of energy in the long-term (Kessler, 2002). After analysing the literature concerning the arguments behind the United Kingdom's renewable power technologies, this research will now concentrate on one of these new methods: wind energy. Public questionnaires and interviews, document review about the visual impact, together with wind farm sound data examination will shape the argument of this dissertation.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

Wind farms apply to many different branches of science and are a complicated area to explore. For this reason, it is useful to employ a number of methods to gain knowledge (Pasqualatti, Gipe and Righter, 2002a). The methods were selected as an investigative approach for acquiring knowledge. This study follows a mixed method approach, focusing mainly on qualitative methods. In addition, some quantitative methods were needed as a complementary background for investigating the whole aspect of this subject; these included measuring sound.

The Study Location

The study area was focused on the Triton Knoll offshore wind farm and associated onshore developments. Triton Knoll Offshore Wind Farm is a proposed site and is being developed by RWE npower renewables Company who obtained development permission from the Crown Estate, the owner of the marine bed in the UK (Wilson and Ireland, 2010).

The Triton Knoll location is situated about 33 km off the beach of Lincolnshire and 46 km from the shore of Norfolk. Between 150 and 333 offshore wind turbines will be constructed. The precise quantity will depend on the turbines' generation capacity. The project will consist also of an onshore electricity substation, potentially underground cables, observing masts and cables under the seabed. The wind farm generation capacity is about 1,200 megawatts, whereby 898,000 typical UK households could be supplied by electricity annually (Wilson and Ireland, 2010).

First electricity production is expected to launch in 2018. The company will start substation construction within three years of 2018. Triton Knoll Offshore Wind Farm needs a proposed substation to be constructed in order to transfer electricity to a voltage suitable for further linking to the general electricity grid. One onshore substation location is needed by the RWE npower renewables company in East Lindsey, Lincolnshire. East Lindsey was recognised also by the National Grid as the suitable site for Triton Knoll to link to the electricity grid. A procedure of public involvement began by RWE npower renewables since 2009. The

involvement comprised of the environmental agencies, local councils and Natural England. Thirteen primary potential zones for the site of the substation were identified after early observations on the natural environment and the landscape of East Lindsey. Four different zones in which to locate the substation are planned and RWE npower renewables are now carrying out a public consultation for each of the four zones. For this study, the Blue Zone Onshore Substation was chosen.

A zone of up to 16 hectares will be needed for the substation equipment. Each of the potential zones is greater than 16 hectares, which offers some flexibility as to where the substation can be located within the zone. The substation will not require any vast buildings. However, an entire floor is needed for maintenance and welfare services. The highest point of the substation will be around thirty metres high. However, most of the objects are estimated to be lower than 10 meters high. Much of the zone will be unused and is likely to be covered with small stones because lots of the space between the electrical equipment will be unused. Access roads will be constructed all the way to the substation in order to transport the heavy components required for the substation and afford entry to the national grid for maintenance purposes.

Figure 4: Blue zone map in great steeping, zone location and description (RPS Planning & Development, 2010).

Figure 5: Aerial map demonstrating Blue zone border

Summary

The Blue Zone is situated around 1.5km south of Great Steeping at National Grid Reference TF445633 (Figure 4 and Figure 5). The zone is between 2 and 5m above sea level, on the North side of the River Steeping. It includes arable areas covering an area of 46.36 ha. There are about 17 residences or potential residences within 400m of the zone border (Table 4) (RPS Planning & Development, 2010).

Table 4: Distance of properties from the border of the Blue zone

Distance from border (metres)	Property name / number (if known)
180	Hall Farm
290	2 on Bartons Lane
300 - 400	3 on Bakers Lane
300 - 400	11 on Ings Lane

During the interview with RWE npower renewables representatives, Steven Brown states that the potential key environmental problems related to the Blue Zone are: The potential access path; the possible visual impact on Little Steeping and nearby farms.

Zone Location and its Description

The North-South dimensions of the zone are 400m. The East-West dimensions of the zone are approximately 1, 150m. The zone is a rectangular shape. The topography and sloping of the zone is level area, rising towards the north (RPS Planning & Development, 2010).

Zone Characteristics

Around 17 dwellings are within 400m of the zone border. Hall Farm on Penfold Lane; Great Steeping (180m); 2 on Bartons Lane, Firsby (290m); 3 on Bakers Lane, Great Steeping (300-400m); 11 on Ings Lane, Little Steeping (300-400m). According to Brown, if the location was to be developed it would not result in disruption of any public way (BOAT, byway, bridleway, and footpath), no disruption of any agricultural path. If the zone was developed, it could have an adverse impact on the local economy that is generated from agriculture (RPS Planning & Development, 2010).

Primary Data

Questionnaire: Public Opinion

For this dissertation, it is imperative to observe the public opinion of those individuals who may be affected by wind farm progression. Consequently, the decision was made to investigate residents' opinion by distributing a questionnaire to people inhabiting the area surrounded by the proposed wind turbine substation in Greet Steeping. The ultimate goal of this questionnaire was to acquire quantitative and qualitative data, with the hope of illustrating the diverse views people hold regarding wind farms in relation to their visual effects, the impact on the local environment and their contribution to a pure and more sustainable energy. The questionnaire's primary focus was limited to a proposed substation location. A number of closed and open-ended questions were included within the questionnaire as Kitchin and Tate (2000) state that '...open ended questions better reflect a person's own thinking'.

Three main topics were included when drafting the questionnaires: public knowledge about renewable power methods, general attitudes toward wind farm development and lastly how residents have been affected by wind farms. The questions follow the questionnaire of Pottinger (2006) for Baillie Wind farm. The study began with a pilot questionnaire where the structure for the questionnaire and suggested questions to be included in the questionnaire were defined. The questions were initially broad but were later narrowed to be more specific. The narrower the question, the more accurately respondents' understanding is reflected. For example, the questionnaire starts with one general question regarding to what extent people support or oppose the use of renewable energy generation. The questions then start to become more specific, for example 'when you last saw a wind farm in operation would you say this had a positive or negative effect', which signals whether the respondents have essential

understanding. A form of the questionnaire and a participant consent form can be found in Appendix B. Some data about age, occupation and ownership status were collected.

The Sampling Method

The target group were residents in the blue potential zone (the Great Steeping village). Selecting participants was done via the pragmatic sampling method; namely, walking around the zone and finding people who were willing to answer (Gunner and Alexov, 2000). It was done during their lunchtime, as the highest variation of people was found during that time. The data was collected face-to-face, as it seems more effective than online or postal questionnaires (Nulty, 2008). As it is nearly impossible to interview everybody, this questionnaire had a desired sample size of 200 participants. The intention was to select participants from a range of different age groups and from both genders. The geographical boundary of the study was within 6 Kilometres around the potential zone.

The pilot sample consisted of 9 participants who completed the questionnaire and offered feedback about the structure. According to this feedback, the questionnaire is easy to follow and is designed to systematically examine respondents' knowledge. Some said it was quick to answer as it only took around two to three minutes to complete, thus keeping the respondent's attention. Some noted that most of the questions are multiple choices and concise, so they do not require much effort to answer.

The main advantages of using the pragmatic sampling method is that it saves a lot of time and obtaining the required data from a specific location is achievable. Moreover, the respondent rate is higher compared to sending the questionnaire by e-mail. It is true that pragmatic sampling can potentially be subject to bias. However it is important to note that this questionnaire was distributed to people whom were selected based on their willingness to participate. Therefore, the data yielded is reliable because participants were willing to answer and were not coerced to do so. This afforded more freedom to participants in choosing the answer that they fully agree with.

The main indicator that the questionnaire method was effective is that all 200 questionnaires were completed. If the questionnaires were sent via post, it is likely the respondent rate would not be 100%.

Semi-structured interviews

A different process for the semi-structured interviews was developed for each target group of interviewees to ensure that different aspects were covered. The aim was to get as many face-to-face interviews as possible with all stakeholders involved in this project. The interview targeted the action group representatives against the wind farm substation, representatives of the local communities, local government representatives, directors of the environmental agencies who work at the site, representatives from RWE npower renewable, the constructor Company and people who live in the study area. When contacting people in order to arrange interviews, a summary of the study was outlined along with detailed explanations of the interview questions and the statement of privacy (see Appendix E)

The questions were mainly concerned with the impact that the substation will have on the local environment and how they personally imagined the substation would influence the local landscape, people's activities in the area and their access to it. Satellite maps were also used to gain data on the potential impact on the landscape.

The potential substation was included on the map along with familiar landmarks on the landscape; therefore it was easier to read. In order to gather all interviewee's notes on the map, a transparent sheet was used to cover the map for each participant. If there were places that people think will be negatively affected by the substation, they were marked with an 'X'; places which may be positively affected were marked with a 'P'. If participants believed that property would gain more value they were marked with a 'W' or property that would lose value marked was marked with an 'S'. Then the map was modified on a computer application showing the previous details.

The first group of questions assessed participants' knowledge about the project. The next group of questions directly asked people to assess influence of the substation.

Secondary data

Noise and Land Protection Status assessment

When trying to evaluate onshore environmental impacts of offshore wind farms, it is very significant to study the above-mentioned two elements. All sources used in this section of the evaluation were derived from secondary data, attained from various associations and groups.

Noise

For the next stage of this environmental impact assessment, noise pollution is considered, as it is a big public concern. Figures for noise records taken at Triton Knoll wind farm could not be acquired, as the wind farm has yet to be constructed. Consequently, noise data for the Coal Clough wind farm was chosen as it could be used to examine if such sound emissions are bearable or not. For this reason, secondary sources of noise were attained from Birtwell (2003), a study from the University of Lancaster which presents a questionnaire delivered to the nearby population of Coal Clough Wind farm. Only a portion of the provided data was selected, that of the noise recorded from two turbines on two sequential days from a distance of 350m, as it is the sound heard from areas beyond the distance of 350m that is the main fear. The figures supplied were in the formula of a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. The data chosen for study was copied into another document, from which two graphs were created by way of comparison. Each trend incorporates duration of 30 seconds of recorded noise in decibels units from four recording devices that interpret sound. An average noise level could then be gained by finding the mean for each trend; this value was then relocated onto each display, enabling an interpretation to be done.

Land Protection Status

The data sources for this section are derived from maps and photographs of the substation area, the public's perception of the area via some of the questions included in the questionnaire, interviews, and focus groups, all adopted to investigate the Land Protection Status. A variety of photographic material was gathered for this dissertation as images and photos have been increasingly recognised as valuable source of data by geographers in recent years (Kitchin and Tate, 2000). The photographs have been included in the dissertation, to supply a visual indication for associated results and to convey some data sources. Photographs and maps help to identify Special Scientific Interest (SSSI's) and Special Protection Areas (S.P.A's), in order to assess the potential effect of a wind farm substation on these areas. By employing photographs in this dissertation, it is intended that a comparison

can be made with the other sources, primarily statistical data, which will prove to be of more interest to the reader.

Maps, aerial photos and drawings

The main method for the landscape assessment was the analysis of digital maps in order to locate areas of terrain that can be viewed from a certain point (Heywood, Cornelius and Carver. 1998). In this dissertation, the visual analysis was used to measure the extent of sight intrusion obligated on dwellings around the wind farm substation. To begin with, the exact proposed positions of the Triton knoll Wind Farm Substation had to be obtained. Global Positioning Satellite (G.P.S) positions for the Great Steeping substation were attained by means of secondary data collection from RPS Planning & Development, (2010). As the proposed Great Steeping substation is still not yet approved, such maps were not in existence. Therefore, Global Positioning Satellite (G.P.S) positions map was gained from the residents against Triton Knoll Substation action group. Furthermore, by carefully assessing the maps, the system of electrical network references of these turbine locations were identified and recorded.

Moreover, a visit to the East Lindsey District Council Planning office was necessary in order to collect detailed maps and aerial photos of the proposed wind farm location as well as local plans. Geographic analysis and techniques were employed to examine the data, such as an imaginary line that demonstrates what can be seen, view sheds and basic visualisations. Even though this dissertation primarily concentrates on Triton Knoll wind farm, it is expected that the discussion concerning the environmental impacts and benefits to society can extend to a wider context, when examining current or future UK wind farm locations.

Field trips and data collection

On the 1st of July, a field trip was made to potential sites for the Triton Knoll substation. These are Great Steeping, Monksthorpe (near Bratoft) and Welton Le Marsh. A field trip was also made to Skegness, the place where the Triton Knoll wind farm will be constructed. The aim of the field trips was to gain further insight into the case and to become further acquainted with the area on the ground. Being situated 112.63 kms from Leicester, scheduling appointments was necessary. A representative from RWE npower renewable and Mr Edwards Anderson from the opposition said that they were able to talk about their views and opinions. A detailed message was sent to them to confirm the meeting details along with a summary of the project's aim. The interviews were very extensive and they were recorded on tape after

gaining the permission of the participants. In addition to the oral data, secondary data was also obtained, for example the director of RWE npower renewable provided PowerPoint slides as well as maps and PDF files about the study potential location and the environmental impact assessment study.

In addition, Mr Edwards Anderson provided the study with a plethora of printed information and maps. Both of them were very generous in providing such data and sharing their opinions with the researcher.

Collecting photos of the terrain

It is important to obtain photos and drawings about the location before the construction work will take place in order to examine the amount of danger the natural environment will be exposed to. For this reason, photos of the landscape, biodiversity and flora of the four potential zones were obtained from contacting members from the against Triton Knoll substation action group.

Ethical Considerations

There are many conflicts between the action group and developers. For this reason, questions, which could potentially increase the tension between both sides, were actively avoided. Another important factor when conducting research is confidentiality. The study followed very strict measures to protect people's identity and data. In addition, under no circumstances were participant's opinions cited without their consent. The results were also sent to all participants who were informed of my contact details and occupation.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS

Public Questionnaire

As several comparable questions were put to citizens at the study location, it was appropriate to employ Microsoft Excel to calculate and present the percentage breakdown for answers to each question. Figures 6 to 13 give a visual presentation of the results. As some of the findings were comparable, a decision was made to display these results in pie charts as it is an effective way that allows good analysis of single variable data. Others findings were displayed in bar charts as it is an effective tool of plural variable data analysis.

Figure 6: Q1: To what degree do you agree or disagree to the use of renewable energy generation as part of the UK's electricity supply?

Figure 7: Q2: To what extent do you agree or disagree to the utilization of wind energy as an alternative supply of electricity?

Figure 8: Q3: How would you explain your knowledge of off shore wind farms?

Figure 9: Q4: When you saw a wind farm last working, would you say this had a positive or negative impact on your view of the local region?

Figure 10: Q5: To what degree do you consider the Triton knoll substation could have a positive or negative effect in the following areas: 1 Harnessing sustainable wind energy; 2 Reducing CO₂ emissions; 3 Producing energy locally; 4 Reducing reliance on imported fossil fuels; 5 Providing local construction and maintenance jobs; 6 Business set up and run by local people; 7 It can be easily decommissioned; 8 Public access infrastructure will be provided?

Figure 11: Q6: And specifically, to what extent do you think that the proposal to build a substation for a wind farm at Triton Knoll could have a positive or negative effect on the following: 1 Your perception of the area; 2 Its visual impact on the local scenery and landscape quality; 3 The natural environment; 4 Noise levels in the area; 5 Business activity; 6 Your key recreational activities; 7 Your quality of life; 8 Property values; 9 Health?

Figure 12: Q7: Overall, how would you describe your reaction to the proposal for Triton knoll substation?

Figure 13: Q12: As part of the wind farm development, developers sometimes pay money to the region per megawatt per annum. How do you think this fund is best used?

Wind, Noise and Land Protection Status

It should be emphasised that this section is reliant upon secondary data. A wind farm should be placed in regions located onshore or offshore where wind speeds are steady throughout the year, in order to get the best from them. In the UK, Wind turbine companies have preferred to construct their turbines on locations with an average wind speed of 7.5 m/s or more (Coles and Taylor, 1993).

Price (2004) uses lots of evidence to illustrate that over a proper episode of time, wind speeds at Coal Clough are stable and as can be seen from Figure 14, it seems that the average wind speed is 7.8 m/s at Coal Clough for the four presented months. Correspondingly, noise measurement evaluation must be conducted to guarantee nominal sound annoyance to the surrounding residents, at the time the wind farm commences. The study provided by Birtwell (2003) was displayed in a suitably visual way, to ensure such an assessment of wind-farm related noise can be made. The recorded noise showed in Figure 14 and 15 are from two turbines on two sequential days from a distance of 350m of Coal Clough Wind farm. It can be seen from Figure 14 that the mean noise is 52.64 dB and 52.33 dB for Figure 15.

Wind

Figure 14: A diagram presenting the variation of wind speeds which recorded over a four month period at Coal Clough Wind farm. The recording included all of the 24 wind turbines at the hub height in 2004 (Birtwell, 2004, p21).

Noise

Figure 15: A diagram presenting the average noise assessment recorded at Coal Clough Wind farm, turbine number 5 (Birtwell, 2004, p22).

Figure 16: A diagram presenting the average noise assessment recorded at Coal Clough Wind farm, turbine number 6 (Birtwell, 2004, p23).

Visibility Analysis

Figure 17: A Google map of the substation- the Blue Zone, marked by the local residents and processes in a computer application to show places will be affected by the substation.

As can be seen from the map, the residents are using the area for a multitude of different activities. In general, people drive or walk around the area and there are children paths leading to the schools, which will be negatively affected. In addition, the substation will be seen from the Little Steeping village and recreational fishing will be closed along the periphery of the substation on the river Steeping. School trips to the area will be negatively affected.

Figure 18: This map shows the potential 4 zones and the proposed routes to each of the four substations (Source: Wilson and Ireland, 2010, pp.185- 188).

Figure 19: A map illustrating the proposed paths for underground electrical cables with high voltage to and from Triton Knoll potential substation locations. (Source: Wilson and Ireland, 2010, p.41).

The landscape of the four potential zones and the cable route area consist of sewers close to the sea, ancient models of habitation and more contemporary uses of land. No national or local landscape specific classifications were given to the marsh and fen areas or the coast. On the contrary, further offshore, the Lincolnshire Wolds are classified as an ‘area of outstanding natural beauty’ in the region of which East Lindsey District Council have classified an Area of Great Landscape Value (AGLV) (Wilson and Ireland, 2010).

Figure 20: A Google map of the Blue zone with the Legacy substation combine in such a way that both images are seen simultaneously, to provide a clear example of what the location could look like.

The map, the site visit and the interviews conducted suggest that the zone and the area around it predominantly consists of arable land but also comprises of a range of different habitats, such as grassland and woodland which signals dwellings of species such as amphibians, bats, breeding birds, badger, water voles and reptiles.

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

Public Questionnaire

From the inspection of Figure 6, it appears that most of the sample population hold very strong opinions in favour of the use of renewable energy generation as part of the UK's electricity supply, with that 90% strongly support it. The majority of the residents were in favour of the use of wind power as an alternative source of electricity.

This finding is confirmed in Figure 7, with 61% of the sample population expressing this view. However, 17% of the participants were unable to offer an opinion. Public knowledge about offshore wind farms which can be seen in Figure 8, which is somewhat surprising and pessimistic, as 50 % of the sample possesses minimal knowledge about offshore wind farms, suggesting that they had not previously lived near to a wind farm and they are not aware of its impact on the environment. In addition, 10% knew nothing at all about wind farms; this perhaps indicates that there is a gap between public awareness and reality. Worryingly, developers may take advantage of this gap and establish wind farms on people's property without insuring against the potential impact that the public will face in reality. Only 30% knew a lot.

It is interesting to note that in Figure 9, over one third (40%) of the people questioned stated that when they last saw a wind farm in operation they either felt it has had neither a positive nor negative effect on their perception of the local area, or expressed no opinion either way. This perhaps indicates that the public do not pay too much attention to the wind farm projects and may avoid the negative side of the issues. Twice the number of residents said that an active wind farm has had a broadly positive impact upon the area (20%) than those who identified a negative impact (10%). This possibly shows that residents have been educated to believe that those wind farms are an environmentally friendly development.

It is arguably surprising that only 20% of the respondents thought that visual intrusion was their main concern. On inspection of Figure 20, it can clearly be seen that if a site were deployed at Great Steeping, visual intrusion would be a problem, as this land is an intact ecosystem of Lincolnshire and the substation can be seen from a distance. Further assessment of Great Steeping's respondents shows that opinion on the visual impact of wind farms was very much divided between the five other choices available. Interestingly, the majority of

Great Steeping residents (35%) consider that the substation will have neither a positive nor a negative visual impact. It is clear that they do not pay a lot of attention to such projects.

Figure 10 resulted from replies concerning the environmental advantages offered by wind farm development, and attitudes towards large-scale investments in future renewable energy plans. Of the Great Steeping sample, 80% strongly agreed that wind farms would harness sustainable wind energy, whilst 15% of respondents were not of this opinion. This evokes that people who commonly disagree with wind farms, admit that the implementation of renewable power into Government strategies are essential. Beside noise pollution and ugliness, this technology also emits gases that increase the current amount of greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere that lead to further global warming (Bice, 2008). This can describe 15 % of the responses who completely disagree that wind farm development reduces CO₂ emissions. It is well-acknowledged by the majority that this is the price to pay for existing in an industrialised community (Warren et al., 2005). However, each innovative wind farm will provide a considerable reduction of greenhouse gas emissions annually; estimated by Tomlinson (2004,) who indicates that the operation of Coal Clough Wind farm alone could save more than 21,000 tonnes of Carbon Dioxide and 252 tonnes of Sulphur Dioxide annually, compared to those produced by burning fossil fuels. A large fraction (70%) of residents thought that 'wind doesn't cause pollution' which was the main declaration for defending wind farms, as appeared in Figure 10.

In the area of visual and noise contamination, one could argue in contrast to the previously mentioned statement; however, in the context of the query asked, pollution relates only to detrimental gaseous emissions. These limited statistics alone indicate a massive reimbursement to both the local and worldwide environment, and as mentioned earlier, such savings would help to achieve the Government's 2010 targets for renewable production. Figure 10 illustrates that half of the residents believe that wind farms help to produce energy locally and reduce reliance on imported fossil fuels, while 10% and 20% respectively said that wind turbines are very negative in terms of producing energy locally and reducing reliance on imported fossil fuels. However, the generation capacity of Triton Knoll's wind farm, as appeared in the methods, is about 1,200 megawatts, whereby 898,000 typical UK households could annually be supplied with electricity. This massive amount of electricity, which will be produced locally, contradicts the fear of some respondents, and decreases dependence upon imported fuels. It can also be seen from Figure 10 that the majority (55% and 45% respectively) were very optimistic that this technology will provide local construction and

maintenance jobs and local businesses will be enhanced. This seems true as the construction work will take up to three years and many labourers will be required.

However, this employment period is considered as temporary for 15% of respondents and some of them answered that the construction company would already have their own labour forces, thus, nothing would change for local people. Figure 10, bar 7 demonstrates that 25% of the residents perceive wind turbines as very difficult to decommission, whilst half of the population believe that they can easily be deconstructed. The interview with the RWE npower renewable' representative suggests that it is not difficult to remove turbines from active service compared to removing other forms of renewable energy such as nuclear power plants. Figure 10, bar 8 reveals a wide variation in opinion, 30% agree that the public access infrastructure would be strongly enhanced by the project implementation, while 10% suggest that it would not be the case. As previously mentioned, the project site consists of arable land and all the places around it are an intact ecosystem. Bringing such infrastructure from roads and electricity grids to this area would contribute to the degradation of land and the loss of biodiversity in an area of natural beauty.

Quarter and 15 % of residents hold the perception that the area will be very and slightly positively affected after constructing the wind farms. This is arguably true, as wind farms do not emit any CO₂ emissions or other gases throughout their operation (EWEA, 2003), which leads people to believe that the area will be improved by wind turbines. Only 20 % express the opinion that the area will be altered negatively, reflecting the opinion of Coles and Taylor (1993) who states that they are tall constructions up to 80m in height which can modify the nature of the landscape and predominate over its beauty. Surprisingly, 30% answered very positive and slightly positive, considering wind farms, which they have seen, to have acceptable or a pleasing appearance (Figure 11). Consequently, aesthetical issues do not seem to dominate question responses, as was expected. Figure 11, bar 3 shows 25% believe the natural environment will be strongly affected positively. This disproves activists who said nobody would like a substation for a wind farm. People might see it better than a nuclear power plant. However, ecocentrism advocates are worried about the severe effect upon animals' mortality resultant from wind turbine operation. People who expressed this opinion in the questionnaire account for the same proportion (25%) of the sample. However, as mentioned in the literature review '...electric power transmission wires are sited below the surface of the ground wherever achievable to meaningfully decrease the numbers of bird fatality by the act of killing by electric shock' (Colson, 1995).

Significantly, offshore wind farms are often constructed far from the coast and despite producing noise emissions, their disturbance will not affect people. However, the wave sounds have negative impacts on marine life, such as dolphins (Tougaard, Henriksen and Miller, 2009).

Action groups against wind farms still consider this a big concern. Consequently, it was important to address noise annoyance in this questionnaire. With companies offering a lot of assurance about noise originating from offshore wind farms, noise was thought to be the greatest concern by 15% of respondents, as indicated in Figure 11.

As discussed above, two factors relate to how well a wind farm can be heard; the level of noise produced by the turbine itself and the distance between the turbine site and residents' houses. With the nearest properties standing at nearly forty kilometres away from Triton knoll, the audibility of the wind farm would very likely be not noticeable at all. However, for people who participate in recreation around Triton knoll, and for those with a strong interest in wildlife, noise will likely remain a major concern. Interrupting business activities for Greet Steeping resident's seems to be a minor issue, with only 15% of respondents stating this factor as their primary concern. Not surprisingly, this proportion corresponds to those residents living very close to the proposed substation. Issues relating to the impact of the substation on recreational activities provided a very interesting set of responses. Unpredictably, the majority did not give a direct opinion and 25% said that their recreational activities will be affected positively.

Fifteen percent of the people questioned, stated that their quality of life would be negatively affected, but the majority stated a very positive response, suggesting that residents have learned to accept the wind farm as part of their community and now appreciate the environmental benefits that it offers. Predictably, citizens all over the UK are anxious about the impacts of nearby projects on decreasing their property prices. A massive 65% of the Greet Steeping sample is certain that the value of their properties will be lowered. This possibly, accounts for the majority of the opposition to the proposed wind farm substation. However, 5% of the participants now believe it will have a positive impact on the value of their houses, but it is unclear as to why they believe that. Arguably unsurprisingly, almost three quarters of the sample population failed to provide an opinion about whether their health would be affected if the substation were to be installed there (Figure 11); nevertheless, 10% of

the participants feel that their health will be very negatively affected. After a rigorous analysis of the site, this appears likely, as few residents know whether they will develop any health problems related to such a development. Keith, Michaud and Bly, (2008) denies any health risks and related them to the noise of the turbines.

The next section of the questionnaire being discussed is based on the question relating to the overall reaction to the proposal for Triton Knoll's substation. Forty percent of the Greet Steeping sample strongly approve of the scheme and feel they will not be affected by the substation (please refer to Figure 12). As expected, well over a quarter of the sample population questioned suggested that their residence would be affected if the wind farm substation were to be installed there, yet 20% of these people neither approved nor resisted. After a precise analysis of the location, this seems likely, as many inhabitants live very close to the Greet Steeping substation; therefore, traffic, noise and annoyance over the 3-year development period may cause significant inconvenience. From the inspection of Figure 13, it appears that the sample population hold very different opinions towards the money generated by the region (per megawatt, per annum) from the wind farm development. The majority agreed that the money should go to further education funding assistance for students, whilst 25% supported it going to local community organisations and events and 15% wanted it to contribute to activities for the elderly. All people responded to this question, which indicates that there are willing to get something positive back regardless of noise at the construction stage, damage to the ecosystem of the area (Keith, Michaud and Bly, 2008).

Overall, the data generated by the 200 completed questionnaires implies that the collated findings displayed above represent the people who were surveyed. There are limitations as to the reliability of the data obtained, not to state the scale of the study undertaken. It is accurate that a larger number of questionnaires could have been distributed to yield more replies and consequently, a more comprehensive data of public attitudes. The number of new people choosing to relocate near the substation will increase annually as houses are sold, and such individuals may have a different outlook. In hindsight, a slight rephrasing of a number of the questions would have decreased any lack of clarity and consequently, produced results that are more precise.

Noise

Sound data gained from Birtwell (2004) in the area of its impact on local inhabitants was quite complicated to analyse. As demonstrated above, the BWEA maintains that the turbine sound from a distance of 350m should be from 35 to 45dB. Upon viewing data Figure 15 and Figure 16, it can be seen that all sound recordings obtained from a distance of 350m were higher than the sound range clearly described by BWEA; therefore, what is the significance of this finding? Birtwell (2004) indicates that the devices that were used to record noise had an adjusted sound recording range from 50 to 100dB and consequently, this is why no recordings lower than 45dB were obtained. Hence, several of the recordings may have indeed been lesser on the ground. If this is the case, the calculated noise levels demonstrated in Figure 15 and Figure 16, may well have fallen within the BWEA's range for turbine noise, heard from a 350m distance.

Semi-structured interviews and map analysis

Upon analysing the interviews, there is a large disparity between developers and protestors, in terms of the substation's impact on the landscape. However, developers see the substation's impact in a very narrow sense and they claim that the potential four zones for the substation were chosen very carefully to minimise the impact on the landscape. For example, the RWE npower renewable' representative Clark Warden stated, 'the blue zone at Greet Steeping is an agricultural land and there are no places of protected areas or areas of special scientific interest within the proposed four zones'. Warden stated again that 'the blue zone at Greet Steeping comprises more than 20 ha of the 'best and most versatile' agricultural fields in MAFF ALC grade 1, 2 and 3a'. Although, the substation area is an agricultural field, the residents are using the area for a multitude of different activities, as showed in figure 17. In contrast to what Warden said, protestors feel that the area should not be looked at in isolation. Indeed, Mr Edwards Anderson, a Chairman of a Wind Farm Action Group, seems to hold a more pragmatic outlook 'you have got basically an intact raw landscape which stayed as it is now for hundreds of years;' namely, the substation impact should be looked at as an invasion of landscape as a whole.

Much the same pattern was identified with attitudes towards the natural environment. For example, developers comprehend the substation's impact on the landscape from their own viewpoint, as illustrated by Warden who stated that 'we tried to be environmentally friendly as much as possible, these procedures add additional cost to the project, for example all grids were designed to be underground, this will be a great achievement toward the natural

environment.’ On the other hand, it is evident that Triton Knoll will dramatically alter the area from unspoilt landscape to one of huge industrialisation and this substation cannot be examined in isolation. Appendix C provides a clear example of photos show the biodiversity in the study location which will be affected by the substation. Anderson noted that ‘the whole area is being targeting for onshore wind farms as well as there is a small 30 m power line and the main concern is not just the substation but also the pylons and associated with infrastructure that going to run as well around the coast of Lincolnshire from unspoilt landscape to one of huge industrialization and the real issue here is obviously the local landscape but also the pylons’. Anderson explained that ‘they will be coming forward from the substation and it will seriously impact on the Lincolnshire woods, an area that was recognized as a natural beauty site.’ Jones Williams shares the same view, despite being a wind farm developer, owning his own tow turbines and working for different wind power companies, proffering that ‘the substation will look very ugly and it is difficult to hide it from being seen from a long distance.’ This suggests, the problem relates to introducing this industry to an intact ecosystem and not about the method in which this industry will be introduced. Appendix C shows a photo of what part of an electricity substation could look like and another photo for Legacy National Grid Substation which proof that the substation will look ugly.

Technocentrism considers wind farm construction as a magic solution for humanity in terms of preventing global warming and providing electricity. What wind farm developers don’t want people to know are a host of problems related to wind farm operations. This was clearly identified by Anderson, the developers, the local authorities, the campaign for the protection of rural England CTRE and even the World Countryside Service who have looked at the in-depth information. On the other hand, developers are to some extent, aware of the visual impacts; for example, Warden explains that ‘the potential key environmental issues associated with the Blue Zone are: the potential access route; the possible visual impact on Little Steeping and the farms around’. This reveals the extent of the developer's efforts to reach a compromise amongst both groups. Williams (a developer) also mentions that, ‘it is better to surround the area of the substation by trees to reduce the visual impact’. This can reduce Anderson’s worries about tourism: ‘but also in a wider content you have got a change in the landscape character of the whole area that will affect tourism as well’. Even though developers offer some assurance regarding visual impact issues, there is currently no verification from RWE npower renewable concerning an assessment of the health impacts of the substation. Therefore, perhaps health-related issues will be of future concern for the local

people. Indeed, Anderson raises a very important question ‘what sort of provision can be made and sort of monitoring is going to be made by the department of health and the developers?’

CONCLUSION

Upon analysis of the various data, it is likely that there will be a considerable effect on landscape substances and visual receivers. This will comprise of a temporary loss of vegetation resulting from cable laying and landing and the visual impacts directly associated with the substation. Perhaps there will be some mitigating methods to decrease the effects of the project on the landscape. This will possibly consist of the re-cultivation of vegetation, such as planting a tree fence around the substation and installing cables underground. However, this does not mean that the intact ecosystem of the area will not turn into an area of mass industrialisation. It is likely that the development will have a substantial impact on both nature and ecological conservation. This may comprise of damage to any existing species or habitats resulting directly from the heavy equipment of the substation and those along the cable route; loss of habitats due to installation or maintenance work; fragmentation of habitats and the isolation of species and the pollution of ecosystems due to the construction and operation process. However, it is unlikely that noise should be a concern for the local residents, as the turbines distance from the shore is 40.5 km.

The questionnaire’s data revealed the overall finding that people in Great Steeping expressed true love of their natural environment and the way they are using it. The majority support renewable energy including wind power, as they believe it can reduce CO₂ emissions and wind farm structures can easily be deconstructed. The majority also considered that when compared to other methods of producing energy, the substation would have neither a positive nor a negative impact on the landscape, natural environment, and noise levels in the area, business activities and recreational activities. It can also be noted, that despite people believing that the substation will reduce property value, they still hold wind farms in higher esteem than other industries.

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ANNEX

Reflection on Methods Used

Sending the questionnaires by e-mail was considered at the design stage and a sample was sent to some people. However, the respondent rate was around 1%. Therefore, it should be noted that people are unwilling to reply online. One lesson learned is that people tend to answer only a few questions in total if they are given the questionnaire and asked to fill it in themselves. Therefore, the questionnaire was read to people and they were then asked to choose from the options. However, some questions needed further development, according to the pilot. For example, in reference to questions 5 and 6, some respondents did not know anything about the advantages and disadvantages of wind farms, therefore 'do not know' was later included.

Not defining the target age group would have been a disadvantage because some of the questions would be difficult for children to understand, therefore people over 16 were targeted, which was determined by an inclusion of a question about their age. Finally, it was preferable to add the following statement at the end of question 5: 'other please write in', as it may indicate if the respondent holds further knowledge. The above points were amended in order to fulfil the aims of this questionnaire, so that validation of this questionnaire could be achieved. As some of the findings were instantaneously comparable, it seemed logical that the suitable method to display these results would be pie charts and bar charts as they are both visually successful forms of single erratic analysis.

Numerous difficulties were encountered in obtaining data. For example, it was very difficult to arrange meetings with people as it was the summer vacation and people were enjoying trips as Greet Steeping is close to Skegness beach. Thus, the decision was made to follow people to the Skegness coast in order to conduct some interviews. A mixed gender of men and women agreed to be interviewed; however, it was very difficult to approach the age group of 20 to 34, maybe because they thought answering questions whilst on holiday is boring. Marking on maps was very interesting to many of the interviewees, who seemed to find it enjoyable. Another legitimate concern was the reliability; some errors and disparities were noticed on the drawings. For example, people disagreed about the fishing area and whether it would or would not be affected by the substation. However, this was not a big issue as the aim was to ask people to draw their favourite places in the area. Another problem was that people found

it somewhat difficult to provide information and to share their memories and ambitions about the location to/with a stranger. To try to counteract this, a detailed explanation and a letter from the University legitimising the project was given to participants. However, this caused some delay in the project in total.

Perhaps it was better to employ some other methods which can result in more critical content. For example, a comparison could be used between Triton Knoll and other off shore wind farms in operation. People living beside a wind farm in operation experience its impact on landscape, health and other factors on the ground. Bird count methods are recommended, such as going to an operation wind farm substation and counting the number of birds that died from electrical shock. A potential study that was thought about in the area was one of the impacts of the substation on the temperature of the area, and the discharge which could affect the local biodiversity. However, due to time limitation these methods were not used.

Reflection on Data Analysis

It would have been more suitable if the study could take into account participants' information in the analysis process such as age and gender, like that undertaken by Krohn and Damborg (1999) who for example state that "men believe that turbines are noisier than women do. People with no specific experiences with wind power believe that noise is louder than those who actually live beside turbines". The results could then achieve more critical finding and conclusion.

Other methods that could have been used to provide improved conclusion have been to interview policy makers to compare if their answers were the same or not to that of the general public. It was questionable to know whether any of interviewees were aware of any costs that need to be applied for protecting the environment if action was taken to construct the substation, or if interviewees had further knowledge about the costs. Additionally, it would be useful to re-test the same participants a few month later to see if their views have changed.

The collected data was coded by referring to each value with a specific format in Microsoft Excel in order to analyze them. A scheme was designed as a database of the questionnaire in order to record the answers; it helped to make calculations of respondents' answers, thus, making the analysis process much easier. However, this required a new skill to be researched and learnt, which consumed more time on the timetable of the research. An example of the

design structure for the questionnaire can be found in the Appendix B. If more interviews have been carried out, then analysis by use of statistical methods could have been used, which would have created a more trustworthy source of data for analysis. The analysis of the maps was based on the interpretation of the researcher. Therefore, some result can be bias and subjective.

Reflection on Scope and Design of the Study

The reason for this study was to investigate and evaluate the onshore environmental impact of offshore wind farms. In recent years the debate, attention and discussion around wind farms environmental impact have been increased. Then, why there is still a need to write more about wind farms among all these entire crowd of publications which has come into sight discussing this subject? The environmental impact has been looked at for onshore and onshore wind farms. However, there are limited literatures about onshore environmental impact of offshore wind farms, especially regarding public opinion, as it still subjects to debate. The study aimed to investigate local community opinions concerning the onshore environmental impacts, resultant from offshore wind developments, with the intention of considerate the reasons underpinning the worries and concerns. It focused, in particular, upon quantifying certain key aspects of environmental problems that can result from wind farm-related plans and projects.

This research question showed in the beginning of this dissertation could be seen from some readers as a general question. Relevant methodology was decided to each section of the research, under the titles: community attitude, visibility analysis, noise, and land protection position. This categorize could help for the research to be more focused. The first step was to design a questionnaire to investigate community attitude. Even though 200 questionnaires were obtained, other parts of the research were still not covered sufficiently. Consequently, research was done to figure out who are the groups (for and against) the development in the location and an interview targeting them was designed. In order to adequately answer the research question, secondary data was employed for visibility and noise analysis. It was difficult to compare the primary data gathered to the secondary data obtained from the literature as a result of the lack of previous study. In addition, if more expansion could have been provided for the secondary data, greater interpretations would be obtained.

Reflection on Writing a Thesis

One of the most challenging elements in writing this dissertation was deciding the structure as no previous dissertation in the same area was found. In addition, it was difficult to decide which part to include in each section as the data obtained was very extended, which makes it hard to keep under the word limit and never lose quality.

The abstract was not as easy as it was thought. Summarizing the whole aspect of the dissertation in a non technical language and keeping the words under the limit was challenging.

Some data for the study were obtained through interviews and it was difficult to decide where to put this data, in the methods or in the result part, as doing interviews was mentioned later in the methods.

Graphs have been used to present the findings. Figure 10 and Figure 11 graphs combined loads of aspects which may make it more difficult to read for some people and cause confusion. Therefore, designing a separate graph for each section perhaps makes the findings easier to follow. Many journals have been read to conduct this research, which have helped in developing the skills or writing academic papers. However, more writing practices were needed to ensure a high standard outcome. Most social science dissertations have the findings and the discussion in one part, it was decided to present them separately in this dissertation as it was thought that a more critical interpretation can be achieved this way.

Modification of maps and designing graphs require professionals in graphic design and doing it individually reduced the quality of the presentation of the dissertation. Therefore, another skill was required.

Data obtained in the finding was very extended. A great challenge was to select the relevant data to include according to the specific audience. Such methods were used to reach ways in which it can consider how to meet an audience's requirements and objectives in the area of Geography.

APPENDIX A

The motivation for this dissertation

The screenshot shows the National Trust website with the following elements:

- Header:** National Trust logo, navigation links (Home, About us, Accessibility, Sitemap), and a search bar.
- Secondary Navigation:** Places to visit, Events, Become a member, Local to you, Donate now, Shop, News, Newsletter.
- Category Navigation:** VISITS & HOLIDAYS, CONSERVATION, HERITAGE & LEARNING, GET INVOLVED.
- Left Sidebar:** A vertical menu with categories: NEWS, LOCAL TO YOU, EAST MIDLANDS, PLACES TO VISIT, LOCAL EVENTS, LOCAL NEWS, MIDLANDS FRESH AIR, VOLUNTEERING, SCHOOLS & TEACHERS, BOOK A TALK, ACCOMMODATION, SHOPS, TEA-ROOMS & RESTAURANTS, PEAK DISTRICT, POLICY, WEDDINGS IN THE LOCAL AREA, SUPPORTER GROUPS, CONTACT US, and HIRING A VENUE.
- Main Content:**
 - Title:** Triton Knoll Offshore Wind Farm
 - Text:** RWE is proposing to build an offshore wind farm at Triton Knoll. The Trust has sought to take an active role in the proposals and has been involved in discussions, correspondence and held meetings with RWE and met the National Grid to fully understand the likely impacts of the proposals. This has included gaining an understanding of the likely wider development needs that would be associated with this project including cabling, overhead power lines and a National Grid substation, none of which are made clear in the current proposals from RWE which simply focus on possible sites for an RWE substation without fully illustrating the wider picture. Following its consultation process the National Trust has submitted a formal objection to the plans given the impact the development would have on the Gunby Estate and Monksthorpe Chapel, both owned and cared for by the Trust.
 - Image:** A photograph of a white wind turbine against a blue sky, with a person visible on the nacelle. A small 'Vestas' logo is visible on the nacelle. The image is credited to ©National Trust.
- Share it:** Social media sharing buttons for Twitter (0 tweets) and Facebook (0 shares).

An article on the National Trust website-Triton Knoll Offshore Wind Farm

APPENDIX B

QUESTIONNAIRE ON WIND FARMS IMPACT

Dear Sir/ Madam,

I'm a postgraduate student in the Department of Geography, University of Leicester . For my dissertation which is part of my study I am carrying out a questionnaire survey about the onshore environmental impacts of offshore wind farms: (A case study of Triton knoll). I have seen the 'Residents against Triton Knoll substation' group on Facebook and I am interested in finding out more about the concerns shown by local residents towards the proposed siting of wind turbines on Triton Knoll. I am aware of the debate which surrounds this controversial issue. I would be very grateful if you could spend a few minutes filling in the following questionnaire (adding any extra comments where necessary) and sending your responses to me by the email provided. Thank you for your time.

Watek Zair

Q1. To what extent do you support or oppose the use of renewable energy generation as part of the UK's electricity supply? **Please choose one option only**

- | | |
|-------------------------------|--------------------|
| 1. Strongly support | 2. Tend to support |
| 3. Neither support nor oppose | 4. Tend to oppose |
| 5. Strongly oppose | |

Q2. To what extent do you support or oppose the use of wind power as an alternative source of electricity? **Please choose one option only**

- | | |
|-------------------------------|--------------------|
| 1. Strongly support | 2. Tend to support |
| 3. Neither support nor oppose | 4. Tend to oppose |
| 5. Strongly oppose | |

Q3. How would you describe your knowledge of off shore wind farms? **Please choose one option only**

- | | |
|---------------------|------------------------|
| 1. Know a lot | 2. Know a little |
| 3. Know very little | 4. Know nothing at all |

Q4. When you last saw a wind farm in operation would you say this had a positive or negative effect on your perception of the local area? **Please choose one option only**

- | | |
|----------------------------------|----------------------|
| 1. Very positive | 2. Slightly positive |
| 3. Neither positive nor negative | 4. Slightly negative |
| 5. Very negative | |

Q5. To what extent do you feel the Triton knoll substation could have a positive or negative impact in the following areas?

Please chose one option only for each category below	1. Very positive	2. Quite positive	3. Neither positive nor negative	4. Quite negative	5. Very negative	6. Don't know
Harnessing sustainable wind energy						
Reducing CO ₂ emissions						
Producing energy locally						
Reducing reliance on imported fossil fuels						
Providing local construction and maintenance jobs						
Business set up and run by local people						
It can be easily decommissioned						
Public access infrastructure will be provided						
Other please write in						

Q6. And particularly, to what extent do you believe that the proposal to construct a substation for a wind farm at Triton Knoll could have a positive or negative impact on the following:

Please chose one option only for each category below	1. Very positive	2. Quite positive	3. Neither positive nor negative	4. Quite negative	5. Very negative	6. Don't know
Your perception of the area						
Its visual impact on the local scenery and landscape quality						
The natural environment						
Noise levels in the area						
Business activity						
Your key recreational activities						
Your quality of life						
Property values						
Health						
Other please write in						

Q7. Overall, how would you describe your reaction to the proposal for Triton knoll substation? **Please choose one option only**

- | | |
|------------------------------------|-----------------------|
| 1. Strongly approving | 2. Slightly approving |
| 3. Neither approving nor resistant | 4. Slightly resistant |
| 5. Very resistant | |

Finally so that we are able to include the views of people from across the community, please can you tell us about yourself?

Q8. Which of the following best describes your residential status? **Please choose all that apply**

- 1. Permanent resident
- 2. Temporary resident
- 3. Visitor
- 4. Local representative of local, regional or national Body
- 5. Non-local representative of local, regional or national body

Q9. How old are you? **Please choose one option only**

- 1. 0-15yrs
- 2. 16-24yrs
- 3. 25-39yrs
- 4. 40-59yrs
- 5. 60 plus

Q10. Are you male or female

Q11. How long have you lived near Triton knoll substation? **Please choose one option only.**

- Born here
- Over 20 years
- Over 5 years
- Over 30 years
- Over 10 years

Q12. As part of the wind farm development, developers sometimes pay money to the region per megawatt per annum. How do you think this fund is best used

1. Further Education funding assistance for students	5. Support for local public transport
2. Business start-up assistance	6. Leisure and sports facilities
3. Home energy savings measures	7. Support for local community organizations and events
4. Activities for the elderly	8. Assistance for school education trips

Something else

.....
.....
.....
.....

Confidentiality and Use of Data

Data will be used in a dissertation which will be used for the purposes of assessment and accessed only by me and members of staff in the Department of Geography - plus the data appearing in the report will be anonymised. Written notes will be completely erased after writing the dissertation.

Research Participant Information

If you have questions, you are free to ask them now. If you have questions later, please feel free to contact me. Email will guarantee the quickest response:

WATHEK ZAIR
Department of Geography
University of Leicester
Address; John Frears House 30 St. James Road Leicester LE2 1HQ
Phone: 07586586055
WZ34@le.ac.uk

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM
Written Consent Agreement and Signature Sheet
Study Participation

Are you interested in participating in this study? Yes / No

Consent to Use Name

Would you mind telling us your true name, (note that the data appearing in the report will be anonymised)? Yes / No

Signature to agree to name use

Name

Consent to Record Interview

Consent to Quote from Questionnaire

I may wish to use this questionnaire for my dissertation and may quote from it in the future for either presentations or articles resulting from this work. The data appearing in the paper and further quotes from it will be anonymised. Do you agree to allow me to quote from this questionnaire? Yes / No

Any Caveats to the Use of Your Questionnaire? Please note any contingencies here.

Consent to Follow-Up questionnaire

I may wish to contact you in the future in order to clarify items and ask for further information. This may also be done by phone or email. Do you agree to allow me to contact you for a follow-up? Yes / No

Please read and initial the following statements

_____ I understand that this questionnaire is intended for the study of the impacts of wind farms on the environment in the UK by Mr Wathek Zair.

_____ I approve of the use of my personal information as agreed upon with the above conditions.

_____ Subject to the confidentiality conditions, I authorize Mr Wathek Zair to use this questionnaire for his paper.

_____ the questionnaire will be electronically recorded on a computer.

Name

Signature

Date

Reporting of Results

Note: this is a separate form that will not be included with the subject questionnaire or identifying data. This is simply to gather data for dissemination of results.

If you are interested in hearing directly back from me with the results of the study, please provide some contact information.

Please provide your name and either mailing address or your email for an update on the finished work.

Name:

Mailing Address:

Email:

Thank You

APPENDIX C

Photos of the flora and fauna in the proposed zones area

The photos show the biodiversity in the study location.

Grey Squirrel in the Green Zone, Welton le Marsh taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010.

Cardinal Beetle taken by the Green Zone site, Welton le Marsh taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010

A Pheasant at Welton le Marsh taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010

Black Pheasant, Welton le Marsh, taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010.

Small Tortoiseshell Butterfly taken just by the Green Zone site, Welton le Mars taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010

An early Purple Orchid, Welton le-Marsh, taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010.

Bluebells in the woods at Welton le Marsh, taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010.

A field of Rape flowers, Welton le Marsh, taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010.

Close-up of Rape flowers, Welton le Marsh, taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010.

APPENDIX D

Photograph shows electricity substations

Legacy National Grid Substation. This substation is near the towns of Wrexham and Rhosllanerchrugog in Wales, taken by residents against Triton Knoll Substation, 2010.

This photograph shows what part of an electricity substation could look like (Wilson and Ireland, 2010)

APPENDIX E

Interview transcript sample

Hello

For my dissertation which is part of my study I am doing an interview about the onshore environmental impacts of offshore wind farms: (A case study of Triton knoll). I have seen the 'Residents against Triton Knoll substation' group on Facebook and I am interested in finding out more the potential environmental impact of the proposed sitting of wind turbines on Triton Knoll. I would be very grateful if you could agree to spend a few times for an interview.

Can you tell about your knowledge of Triton Knoll wind turbine?

I have been actively involved in with fighting turbines for the last three years and I watch carefully the development of offshore. I watch the proposal for triton Knoll which is 333 turbines by RWE npower renewables and they started the planning consultations about a month ago and obviously I have seen the development taking place of the Skegness city as well

How many substations?

One in Skegness and there was a public notice putting into papers which I saw that was at the beginning of July.

Can you tell what impact the substation will have on the environment?

Let's start by recreation activates.

They have not decided yet where the substation is going to go, but this substation it can not taken in isolation, because the whole area is being targeting for onshore wind farms as well and there is a small 30 m power line running up toured further South and the main concern is not just the substation, but also the pylons and associated with infrastructure that going to run as well around the coast of Lincolnshire, from non spoilt landscape to one of huge industrialization and the really issue here is obviously the local landscape, but also the pylons they will be coming forward, if it is approved. It will seriously impact on the Lincolnshire woods, which an area standing natural beauty. It is due to the fact, it will change this part of Lincolnshire substantially and will cause damage to a protected landscape .I do not think the developers or even the local authorities or the campaign for protection rural England CTRE or

even the world country side service have looked at this informed details. There is something the developer trying to avoid being raised is a serious issue. So you have got impact on local residence and a massive industrialization at the locality. But also in a wider content you have got a change in the landscape character of the whole area that will affect tourism as well.

Can you tell me about it is impact on property values?

I think property values will drop possibly between 20 - 30% or even 40% because people choose this area to move to, and local people try to move away but there is evidence that when coming into local area there is essentially an intact landscape, properties prices will go down by minimum of 20 % in some cases.

If you want to buy a house would u buy it near a wind turbine substation?

I would suggest it will be the case. Those people who live near the substation will suffer seriously; I have evidence about a house near a wind farm substation on the market which is unsellable

Can u tell me what impact they have on health ?

I do not know, I am not highly qualified to answer that. I know that there are. If you are talking about the substation in particular, I think that will be a fear for local community. There is substantial structure, alien structures into a completely unspoiled landscape. So health will be an issue for local people and what sort of provision can be made and sort of monitoring is going to be made by the department of health and the developers? I do not know, but if I was living close by I will seriously worried about health issues.

Can you tell me what impact the substation will have on biodiversity?

I do not think it is environmentally friendly. I see other options for environmentally friendly energy production such as wave power, solar panels. Wind is not. In my view it is not sensible economic and way of producing energy the fact that if you have no wind, you have no energy and in the coldest winter when the energy is most wanted 2500 turbines they stood still. This is massive problem on a massive scale, and the problem with offshore particularly is their cost is enormous. We are talking about billions of pounds which is funded by tax payers, there would be no turbine built unless there is subsidies heavily, because there are not commercially viable this project. Offshore and of shore in my view is a total and absolute disaster. It is a catastrophic of the government policy and it case major problems. There will be huge fallout from this. I am saying to you that in 10 years time people will be wondering

what on earth is going on how did this happened it should not be allowed to continue. Biodiversity by all means, new technology with new. We are talking about turbines which imported from Germany from china and involve non UK workers this is a total disaster.

Can you tell me about noise?

Noise offshore is not an issue but offshore is less than 1.5 km. they have the potential to cause serious health issues regarding noise

There will be a noise issue with the substation. Obviously there will be increase traffic but what noise the substation produces, I do not know.

Can you tell me about other environmental impacts?

The triton knoll one is quite away out I think it is 10 to 15 miles offshore. They will have a big visual impact, developer are trying to change the landscape into a massive wind park and trying to get money on the back of governmental subsidies. It is a scandal waiting to be exploding, in my view. It is bigger than the phone hacking scandal because renewable energy supported the way to buy the subsidies, is driving up fuel prices substantially, is increasing fuel poverty. There are figures saying at 30 0000 more people died of fuel poverty last year because of the rise in energy prices

Developers say that the wind farms reduce CO₂ emissions, what do you think about that?

There is no evidence that a single turbine across the UK and across the world substantially reduce CO₂ emissions. If you look at the experience of Europe and look at the experience of the UK coming forward, it is recognize fact that they want 19% of extra capacity to be on standby when the turbines are not working. Obviously when this renewable energy, those power stations scale back down, we have to have a Spanning reserves, gas power station and nuclear power station. This infertility infidelity negates CO₂ emissions and if you research across Europe you will find that now there are saying that because the mix of energy, because of the way turbines work or do not work, CO₂ gained by turbines are being negated by, and need to back up. Thousands tones of concrete have been used. Concrete is the most environmental distractive. We do not know what sort of impact this concrete going to the ground is going to have and obviously you have got the transport coast associated. I question any significant CO₂ gained, It is the wrong technology in the wrong place at the wrong time. This is a complete disaster.

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name

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